

THE ROLE OF INFLAMMATION FACTORS IN THE MECHANISMS OF PROTECTION AND DESTRUCTION OF PERIODONTAL TISSUES

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Abstract. The onset and course of any infectious disease is determined by the strength of the organism's response. The nature of this response depends on the antigen specificity of previously acquired immunity, and is largely determined by human genotype. Only part of the observed reactions to infection can be regarded as protective. In addition, reactions of a neutral nature often occur: reactions that are useless in terms of the body's defense, but deplete the resources of the immune system, as well as autotoxic reactions that cause massive damage and death to the body's own cells and tissues. Often it is autotoxic reactions that determine the pathophysiological picture of the disease as a whole.

Key words: inflammation, periodontal, immune system, dehydration

Introduction. Researches in the field of etiology of both aggressive and chronic periodontitis have led to revelation of the fact of sharp increase in the activity of matrixins (matrix proteinases synthesized by fibroblasts and macrophages in particular) at inflammation of periodontal tissues of any nature. The activity of neutrophil collagenase MMP8 and gelatinase MMP9, the enzymes participating in the final stages of collagen degradation, increases to hundreds or thousands of times. On this basis, most researchers conclude the autoproteolytic nature of the degradation of the connective tissue matrix of the periodontium underlying periodontitis.

Important details of the molecular mechanism of periodontal ligament degradation remain unclear, but apparently the inducer of hyperproduction and hyperactivation of MMP is lymphocytes, which in response to invasion of pathogenic bacteria migrate to areas of the affected periodontium and release pro-inflammatory lymphokines. Some of these lymphokines act on resident fibroblasts and macrophages as inducers. The functional identity of the lymphocytes and the antigens to which they are specific remain unknown, but it can be speculated that the cause of periodontal ligament degradation is the overactivity of lymphocytes infiltrated into the focus of infection, aimed at eliminating the invasion. When considering the effect of MMP8 and MMP9 on the

degradation of the periodontal connective tissue matrix, an important question is the regulatory mechanism of their activity elevation. Most of the works on the experimental investigation of IL8 synthesis induction mechanisms in periodontitis have been performed on human gingival epithelium cell models, in particular, on immortalized OBA-9 cell line or primary gingival fibroblasts.

An example of such work is the article by Savitri I.J. et al. (2014). The authors aimed to investigate the effect of irzoglazine maleate (IM), a well-known inflammatory regulator, on the interaction of gingival epithelial cells with the periodontopathogen *P. gingivalis*. IM has been shown to ameliorate the effect of induction of IL8 synthesis by *P. gingivalis* or its purified polysaccharide on OBA-9 cell culture ($P < 0.01$). Hajishengallis G. et al. (2015) describe a study of lymphokine production under animal models of periodontitis. Using several different models, the authors concluded that IL1, TNF α , prostaglandins, complement components and RANKL were the most important factors to assess periodontal health. At the same time the authors observed differences in the efficiency of induction of the synthesis of these factors by different bacterial pathogens, and the most common cause of periodontitis tended to be dysbacteriosis. The authors cite diabetes and differences in leukocyte adhesiveness as systemic factors in the human body that influence the propensity for periodontitis. Bae W.J. et al (2015) investigated the effect of the hypoxia factor HIF2 α on the inflammatory response and osteoclast differentiation, in particular the correlation between HIF2 α concentration and local levels of inflammatory cytokines and proteolytic enzymes when human gingival fibroblast cultures were stimulated with bacterial lipopolysaccharide (LPS) and nicotine. Cells from CGP patients were found to secrete greater amounts of HIF2 α in response to nicotine and LPS stimulation, with the response increasing in time and increasing with increasing stimulus concentration.

Correa J.D. et al. (2014) describe a study on the effect of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), which has highly sensitive targets outside the nervous system, in particular in the periodontal ligament, dental pulp and odontoblasts, on the course of periodontitis. However, physiological experiments to investigate the effects of BDNF on periodontal health were limited to a regeneration model of mechanically damaged periodontium at the start of the study. Its role in the development of periodontitis was investigated for the first time. The study involved samples of patients with CGP (28 individuals) and with healthy periodontium (29 individuals). By ELISA, BDNF

levels in periodontal flushes were found to be elevated in the CGP group compared to controls.

Conclusions: To summarise, the role of MMP8 and MMP9 in periodontal ligament and alveolar bone degradation needs to be specified, although the statistical relationship between hyperproduction of these matrixin precursors and the severity of periodontitis can be considered proven.

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